

Design, Calculation and Manufacturing of a Rim in Continuous Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics

S. Delaloye, G. Koning

ETH Zürich - Institut für Konstruktion und Bauweisen - Bauweisenlabor
Wagstrasse 13 - CH 8952 Schlieren

Abstract

A continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic rim has been developed for a lightweight electric motorcar. Emphasis has been put on the forming technique, taking into account the manufacturing time, as well as the laminate quality. Based on the experiments, which have been carried out during the forming of the composite rim, a new tooling concept has been developed. Its integration in an automated forming unit will lead to cycle times in the range of twenty minutes for complex shaped parts out of PEEK-carbon fiber laminates.

Keywords : thermoplastic composite rim, diaphragm forming, process automation.

1. Introduction

It has been observed, especially on lightweight vehicles, that a reduction of the non-sprung masses as tyre, rim or braking device strongly improved the driving behaviour. Further the fuel consumption will be reduced as the required energy to accelerate the wheel directly depends on its polar moment of inertia and thus on its mass.

Composite materials with high specific strength and stiffness offer the possibility to design such a lightweight rim. Previous reports /1/ already mentioned the use of fiber reinforced thermosets for the manufacturing of rims. Nevertheless their insufficient toughness could lead to critical failure behaviour /2/. The use of fiber reinforced thermoplastics with improved damage tolerance will solve this specific problem. Moreover thermoplastic composites offer advantages such as fast manufacturing processing or recycling ability, which are of capital importance when mass production is aimed.

2. Design

Two parameters mainly influenced the design of the composite rim :

- the geometrical boundary conditions
- the manufacturing process

The geometrical boundary conditions are given on the car frame's side by the braking device and the five bolts fixation of the rim to the axle. The dimensions of the narrow type tyre with low roll resistance determined the design of the rim bed.

The available manufacturing techniques strongly influence the design of the component, particularly for thermoplastic composites. It has been found already in the early design stage, that diaphragm forming would be a suitable manufacturing technique for the rim with respect to the double curvature of the laminate. Consequently the rim is composed of two half shells, which are bonded together in a second stage. Local thickness increment in the fixation area and in the flanges (fig. 1) are included in the laminate before forming.

3. Calculation

Due to the non-symmetrical loading and fixation of the rim, the whole geometry had to be modelled, which led to a large model with 2672 shell elements and 2655 nodes (fig.2). The following combination of loadcases has been calculated :

- weight forces : 4500 N
- side forces : 3500 N
- breaking forces : 3500 N
- tyre pressure : 10 bar
- rotational speed : 1250 rpm

These loads, provided by the car-manufacturer, have been introduced directly into the rim as face pressures or nodal forces without modelling the tyre. The boundary conditions have been fixed by restraining the six degrees of freedom of the five fixation bolts.

Because of its superior mechanical properties among the commercially available thermoplastic prepregs, APC-2 (AS-4 carbon fibers with PEEK matrix) as unidirectional tape was used for manufacturing the rim. According to the load cases, quasi-isotropic laminates with the following lay-up sequences have been modelled :

- (0, 45, 90, 135)_n
- (0, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150)_n
- (0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 120, 140, 160)_n

Very soon it has been observed [3], that the stiffness was the most critical dimensioning parameter. Large deflections will provoke the tyre to loose air or even the rim to touch the breaking device. Therefore the third lay-up sequence, providing the most uniform bending stiffness, has been chosen for the 2.25 thick (18 plies) symmetrical laminate of each rim shell. An additional 18 plies reinforcement in the flanges and another 36 plies one in the fixation area increased the local stiffness.

Further a ply-by-ply analysis of the laminate has been performed to check for fiber or matrix failure. Non acceptable stress levels have been recorded for several elements in load introduction areas. However this effect has been neglected, as it is probably due to the very local loading, which in fact doesn't reflect the reality.

4. Manufacturing

4.1. Forming

The diaphragm forming technique, which comes from the superplastic forming of metallic sheets, has been used to manufacture the two halves of the rim. In the case of thermoplastic composites, the flat laminate to be formed is fixed under vacuum between two thin plastically deformable polymeric films, the diaphragms, which are clamped around the edges. As the laminate and the diaphragms reach the forming temperature, which is in general higher than the

melting temperature of the thermoplastic matrix, a pressure gradient is applied normal to the diaphragms, causing the part to be formed onto a heated tool. A dwell time at constant temperature allows the laminate to be fully consolidated. The formed part can be taken out from the tool after cooling under pressure until structural stability is achieved.

A controlled fiber placement as well as restricted laminate wrinkling and splitting are possible as the laminate is maintained under biaxial tension during the deformation /4/. Complex curvature parts with homogenous consolidated laminates can be manufactured as the forming and the consolidation processes occur under isostatic pressure above the melting temperature of the matrix.

Before starting the forming process, the laminate and the diaphragms as well as the tool have to reach the forming temperature. For metallic tooling heated by forced convection in autoclaves, the heat up time of the forming tool is mainly influenced by its thermal mass. Previous studies reported the optimum forming temperature of APC-2 laminates to be between 370°C and 400°C /5/. Below 370°C the consolidation of the laminate is not satisfying. Higher temperature than 400°C, although under nitrogen atmosphere, will provoke the thermal degradation of the polymeric diaphragms, however this effect is strongly time dependant. Therefore a compromise has to be found between the forming temperature and the time needed to heat up the tool to this temperature.

Consequently, tools with low thermal mass will lead to shorter cycle times and to reduced thermal degradation of the diaphragms, which will improve by the way their forming behaviour. This effect has been taken into account when designing the forming tools, which have been turned on a CNC-lathe. Unfortunately for manufacturing reasons, the minimum tool thickness was limited to 10 mm. Low heating rates of maximum 10°C/min have been measured on the tool in the hot autoclave, as a result of its high thermal mass. Numerous experiments have shown, the optimum forming temperature to be at 380°C, depending on the heating behaviour of the tool and on its geometry.

Due to the design of the female tool (fig.3), the laminate and the diaphragms have been formed with low pressure (up to 0.3 MPa with an average pressurisation rate of 0.025 MPa/min) as free membranes. Late contact with the tool combined with low forming pressure improved the thickness distribution in the laminate, as matrix flow was reduced. Resulting from the isostatic pressure application through the compliant diaphragms, an homogenous laminate consolidation has been observed even in reinforced areas with increased thickness.

4.2. Bonding

To join the two halves of the rim, the so called "amorphous bonding" method was applied. This requires a thermoplastic matrix as bonding agent with a melt temperature by which the parts to be joined are still structural stable. Therefore the amorphous polyetherimide (glass transition temperature = 216°C) can be used advantageously for bonding semicrystalline PEEK-laminates (glass transition temperature = 143°C, crystallite melting temperature = 334°C). A parametric study has been performed on APC-2 lap shear samples bonded with PEI-film in order to evaluate the influence of the following parameters on the bonding quality :

- bonding temperature
- pressure on the bonding area
- surface treatment of the bonding area

Shear strength values up to 47 MPa have been measured /6/ for optimised process parameters. Further it has been observed, that particularly the surface treatment of the bonding area, as for example sandblasting, which produces a surface increase as well as an activation, strongly influenced the strength values. As this effect is time dependant, the bonding should take place directly after the surface treatment.

According to the previous experiments, the halves of the rim have been sandblasted, a 0.125 mm thin PEI-film has been placed inbetween and finally the parts have been heated up above the PEI-melt temperature. After a short dwell time at low pressure, the bonded rim (fig.4) has been cooled down and trimmed with water-jet.

5. Automated forming machine

Due to the poor efficiency of forced convection heating in the autoclave, the manufacturing time mainly depends on the thermal behaviour of the tool. In order to increase its heating rate, an evaluation of infrared heating has been carried out on lightweight experimental top hat tools. Stainless steel and fiber reinforced ceramic [7] have been selected as tooling material. Heating rates of about 40°C/min have been measured on the 3 mm thick stainless steel tool, which was heated only on one side (heating power density = 50 KW/m²). During the both sides heating of the fiber reinforced ceramic tool, heating rates of more than 100°C/min up to 400°C (heating power density = 2*50 KW/m²) have been recorded, which can lead to drastic reduction of cycle times. Nevertheless the vacuum integrity of such tools is, up to now, not sufficient to form high quality advanced thermoplastic components.

The automation of the forming process is, beside the improvement of the heating method, the only way to reduce further the manufacturing time and consequently the costs. For these reasons, a new diaphragm forming machine (fig.5) has been developed. The main part of the machine consists in a pressure vessel (1000 mm diameter and 1100 mm height) with an integrated infrared heating system. The laminate as well as the tool are heated on both sides with 240 infrared heaters (overall heating power of 95 KW), each of them being controlled independently to assure an homogenous temperature distribution. Fully computer controlled process parameters allow parts with reproducible properties to be formed. Further the machine is equipped with a handling system, which permits the automated placement of the laminate between the diaphragms into the forming unit and the removal of the formed part.

According to the actual configuration of the diaphragm forming machine, APC-2 laminates can be formed to high quality components in less than twenty minutes.

6. Conclusions

The diaphragm forming as well as the amorphous bonding technique have been successfully applied for the manufacturing of a continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic rim. The poor efficiency of forced convection heating in the autoclave has led to a new tooling concept based on lightweight tool with reduced thermal mass, which are heated on both sides with infrared heaters. The integration of this tooling concept in a new automated diaphragm forming machine has led to a drastically reduction of manufacturing time. The optimisation of the process applied to low cost engineering thermoplastic composites will be of great importance for mass production of structural parts as for example in the automotive industry.

7. Acknowledgments

The authors wish to acknowledge hereby the Swiss Government - die Schweizerische Kommission zur Förderung der wissenschaftlichen Forschung - for its financial support.

8. References

- /1/ H.Adam, RWTH Aachen
Entwicklung und Erprobung Glasfaserverstärkter Kunststoffräder für Personenkraftwagen
Proceedings 31th International Man-Made Fibers Congress, Dornbirn 1992
- /2/ A.Cathart
Karbonräder
Motorradzeitschrift MO, January 1992
- /3/ G.Koning, S.Delaloye, ETH Zürich-IKB
Designing, Calculating and Manufacturing of a CFRTP-Wheel
unpublished master thesis, ETH Zürich, December 1992
- /4/ P.J.Mallon, C.M.O'Bradaigh, R.B.Pipes, University of Delaware
Polymeric Diaphragm Forming of Complex Curvatures Thermoplastic Composite Parts
Composites, Volume 20, January 1989
- /5/ C.M.O'Bradaigh, P.J.Mallon, University College Galway, University of Delaware
Effect of Forming Temperature on the Properties of Polymeric Diaphragm Formed
Components
Proceedings ASCM/CCM Joint Symposium on Composite Materials Science and
Engineering, University of Delaware 1987
- /6/ E.Lutz, M.Niedermeier, ETH Zürich-IKB
Ein Beitrag zum Fügen von kontinuierlich kohlefaserverstärkten PEEK-Halbzeugen
mittels PEI
unpublished master thesis, ETH Zürich, December 1990
- /7/ J.Davidovits, M.Davidovics, Geopolymer Institute
Geopolymer : Ultra High Temperature Tooling Material for the Manufacture of Advanced
Composites
Proceedings 32th International Sampe Symposium, San Diego 1991

FIG. 1 : RIM DESIGN

FIG. 2 : FE-MODEL

FIG.3 : FORMING TOOL

FIG.4 : APC-2 RIM

FIG.5 : AUTOMATED DIAPHRAGM FORMING MACHINE